

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK FORMAL SPEECH ETIQUETTE

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Abstract: This article discusses the role of language in our lives and its importance as the main means of communication. It also briefly covers the history of language learning and its structure, as well as explores one of the current topics – the comparative study of languages of completely different cultures. In recent years, world communities have begun to pay special attention to the speech activities of different cultures, peoples and nationalities. The following aspects will be considered:

- Formal greetings;
- Formulas of politeness.

Key words: speech etiquette, formal communication, comparative study, English speech etiquette and Uzbek speech etiquette.

Formal speech etiquette is an integral part of our everyday communication. It defines the rules and norms that we adhere to during communication, especially in formal and business situations. In this article, we will dive into a comparative study of formal speech etiquette in two different languages - English and Uzbek. Analyze and compare basic aspects of etiquette, such as greetings, addresses and other nuances that may differ depending on language and culture. Increasing our knowledge in this area will help us be more polite and confident in intercultural communication.

“It’s not often in everyday life that we think about such a concept as “speech etiquette.” As a rule, a person simply speaks as he thinks or sees fit. In certain cases, such as the loss of loved ones, we try to express condolences to the family using clichés, without realizing that they are a sign of etiquette. But all the phrases have long been thought out and spelled out” (1). So, for example, in the case of a professional promotion, we use a certain text of congratulations in the form of politeness and admiration, without thinking that this is the first sign of etiquette. Speech etiquette can be acquired from early childhood, when a child is taught to thank for a good deed and treat work with respect, understanding values; self-education also contributes to raising the level of etiquette, for example, by studying books, reading various stories, we take examples of politeness and implement them into our daily life. But there is also a case when the skills of communication manners take on the essence in a professional environment, as a certain set of rules should be observed between a superior official and a subordinate. This is how speech etiquette flows into our lives, being used in any form of communication, without any restrictions. As N.I. Formanovskaya, a famous researcher of speech etiquette, said: “Speech etiquette refers to the regulating rules of speech behavior, a system of nationally specific stereotypical, stable communication formulas accepted and prescribed by society to establish contact between interlocutors, maintain and interrupt contact in the chosen tonality” [Formanovskaya, 1987]. (1)

Speech etiquette is a set of rules and norms that govern correct and respectful communication in various situations. It is divided into several categories, but two of them are clearly represented in our lives: Informal and formal communication style. The informal style is used in informal settings, such as when talking with friends or close colleagues. Formal is used more in formal meetings or business situations, such as presentations, interviews or interactions with senior officials .

“Speech etiquette characterizes almost any successful act of communication, and therefore it is associated with the so-called postulates of speech communication, which make the interaction of communication participants possible and successful. These postulates were formulated by the linguist and philosopher G. P. Grice. These include **quality postulates** , which imply that the message must not be false; **quantities** , meaning that the message should be neither too short nor too long; **relationships** - the message must be relevant to the addressee; **and method** : it must be clear, distinct, and not contain words and expressions that are incomprehensible to the addressee” [Grice, 1975]. (1)

In our time, these postulates are initially formed in a narrow circle of the family because parents are the main source and carriers of the rules of etiquette, as every parent wants to ensure that their child occupies higher positions, is a leader in circles among peers and is able to achieve his goals and tasks. And the very first thing they teach is to enter into a dialogue, formulate a proposal correctly, correctly formulate your assumptions and justify your proposals. From a young age, our first colleagues, comrades, co-workers are our parents, and here in dialogue with them we use our formal speech and clearly express our initiative in order to get that same toy or chocolate.

A comparative study of English and Uzbek formal speech etiquette can reveal similarities and differences between the two languages in terms of accepted norms of behavior and expression in various communication situations.

The first thing that is most important is the greeting. In all languages of the world, the greeting can be translated as “I wish you health,” “Have a nice day,” “Good afternoon,” “I wish you peace,” “Light to your home.”

- Since ancient times, the Uzbek people have been considered the most polite and hospitable people, without losing this position today. You can often see how people greet guests with a smile and with all their hearts, offering all the best as it is done with love. When seeing strangers, you can often hear a widely used greeting of the formal type “ Assalomu alaykum ! (Peace for you!), in response to a mutual polite greeting “Vaalaykum assalom!” (And Peace to You!), it is worth noting that the younger person first greets the same way as he shows respect to elders and the first one wishes Peace, that is, the first one greets. Here is a vivid example of greetings:

"Salom! - Hello! ("Salom" means "peace with God")

Assalomu alaykum! - Hello! (a greeting translated from the Koran as “peace be upon you” is used everywhere. These greetings came from Arabic and took root in countries where the majority of the population professes Islam)

Vaalaykum assalom! - Hello! (answer “peace be with you”)

Yaxshimisiz? (Yahshimisiz?) - Are you okay?

Qandaysiz? (Kandaysiz?) - How are you?

Ishlaringiz yaxshimi? (Ishlaringiz yakhshimi?) - How are things going?

Yaxshi yuribsizmi? (Yakhshi yuribsizmi?) - How are you?” (2)

Also, a distinctive feature of the Uzbek greeting is that the left hand is placed on the heart and the head is slightly bowed in front.

For example: consider a case at a business meeting when a man first of all greets the rest of his male colleagues by shaking each other's right hand, while the left hand is also not placed on the heart, and if these are old friends, then after the handshake a friendly hug follows, but with the opposite sex it is not welcome to do this, just nod your head. But women's greetings also differ from men's greetings in that women hug when they meet.

- The British also have a large number of greetings such as: "Good morning, Good afternoon, Good evening - Good morning, Good afternoon, Good evening.

How do you do? How is your Health? How have you been? - How how are you ? How is your health? How are you doing?". (3)

Unlike the Uzbek people, the English-speaking population only gets by with a handshake and, if it is a close acquaintance or distant friend, they usually hug after the greeting. Age and gender do not limit the possibilities; just as a woman can first greet a man by extending her hand, so can a man.

In formal speech etiquette, both in the Uzbek and English languages, it is strictly forbidden to abbreviate words and use colloquial slangs. And for more advanced rhetoric, a complete answer should be given, using certain terminology, and in order to sound more expressive, the construction of a complex sentence is used.

- Politeness is an integral part of the communication process. There is no comparison between Uzbek and English speech etiquette, since in both cases people are always friendly, respectful towards others and polite. The Uzbeks address everyone without exception with " **SIZ** "; this situation is also observed among the British. Why? There is no word "you" in English, so YOU is translated as "YOU" and this is very well reflected in the grammar, you can notice that after YOU comes " ARE ", " WERE " is proof that " **YOU** " is always translated as a plural.

"I am very grateful to **you** - I To you Very grateful

You are always welcome - Always Please

Don't mention it - Not behind What

It's all right - Not costs

Excuse me for making trouble - Sorry behind anxiety

You are so kind - You Very kindly

Be so kind as - Be kind ." (4)

"Good afternoon! (good morning, good evening) - Assalomu alaykum!

Please! - Arzima ydi !

Sorry - Kechirasiz

Is everything good with you ? - Yahshimisiz ?

Welcome! — Xush kelibsiz !

Bon appetit! — Yaxshi tuyadi !

Good night! — Xayrli tun !

Bye! - Xair !

Goodbye! - Korishguncha ! (5)

If we take examples of a business meeting, among Uzbeks it is customary to first let in the older person, even if it is a subordinate; in this situation, respect for the elders is shown. Among the British, the senior person enters first and then the rest enter, this shows respect and veneration for the head of an institution or organization.

“The form of address is also considered the most important: In English, forms of address such as “Mr.” or “Mrs.” (Mrs – Mrs – is used when we talk about a married woman/girl. Used with the woman/girl’s surname.

Miss – miss – is used when we talk about a woman/girl who is not married. Used with the surname of a woman/girl.

Ms – miss – if we do not know whether the girl is married or not. Usually used with a woman's/girl's surname), often used when addressing persons of unknown gender or when addressing someone older or of higher rank.” (6)

“In the Uzbek language, communication is based on the level of upbringing, and options for address may include “respected” or “elder” to show respect for the interlocutor.” (7)

Conclusion.

In conclusion, comparing English and Uzbek formal speech etiquette, the following conclusions can be drawn:

“In both languages, there are certain rules and norms that govern formal communication. They are determined by the cultural and historical characteristics of each language.” (8)

In the Uzbek language, it is more common to directly address the interlocutor by name, without using titles and positions. The looser structure of Uzbek formal speech etiquette may be due to more familiar and friendly communication in Uzbek culture.

Both languages have special expressions and phrases that are used to indicate deference, respect and politeness. In general, a comparative study of English and Uzbek formal speech etiquette allows us to better understand and appreciate the cultural and linguistic characteristics of each language. It also helps develop intercultural communication skills and respect for differences in expressions of respect and politeness.

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